

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL READINESS OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS THROUGH PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT

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Abstract. *The theoretical foundations of the formation of professional readiness of future teachers are considered. The content of psychological and pedagogical support of students is considered. The following methods were used: analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, study and generalization of pedagogical experience of students' pedagogical practice, observations, conversations. The results of the study were highlighted in the form of scientific reports at scientific and practical conferences.*

Keywords: *psychological and pedagogical support, pedagogical system, psychological training, professional readiness.*

The most characteristic feature of the modern concept of teacher training is the increasing role of its psychological orientation as a determining condition for teacher training. New requirements define promising areas of training for teachers of a new type, organically combining a scientific outlook with professionalism, a high level of knowledge in psychology, and readiness for pedagogical work. The formation of professional readiness of future primary school teachers through psychological and pedagogical support is an urgent topic of pedagogy and psychology. Scientists in different countries pay special attention to this, including Uzbekistan. Here is an overview of the works devoted to this topic:

Karimova M.Kh. works on the issues of professional training of teachers, focusing on the introduction of national cultural values and principles into the educational process. Abdullayev A.S. explores the problems of formation of professional competence among students of pedagogical universities through the introduction of innovative educational technologies. Saidova Z.T. considers the importance of psychological and pedagogical support for students of pedagogical specialties for the development of their professional and personal qualities. Ismailova Kh.I. studies aspects of the formation of communicative competencies in future primary school teachers as an important component of their professional readiness.

International studies. John Dewey (USA), a classic of pedagogy, justified the importance of a practical approach in teaching future teachers, as well as the need for psychological support at all stages of training. L.S. Vygotsky (Russia/USSR) developed a cultural and historical theory that focuses on the interaction of learning and development. His ideas are actively used to develop pedagogical skills. K. Rogers (USA) is one of the founders of humanistic psychology, who emphasized the importance of a personality-oriented approach to learning. Jean Piaget (Switzerland) studied the cognitive development of children, which significantly influenced the methods of teaching and training future teachers. K.G. Jung (Switzerland) - his theory of personality types is used to adapt pedagogical activities to the individual characteristics of students. K. Dunker (Germany) studied creativity in thinking, which is important for preparing teachers for non-standard situations in the educational process.

Areas of work and methods:

Case methods and practical tasks: they are widely used to develop students' skills in solving real pedagogical situations.

Psychological and pedagogical support: includes trainings, consultations, reflection, which allows students to realize their own professional goals.

ICT integration: modern educational technologies are being actively introduced into the learning process to prepare students for digital pedagogy.

All disciplines taught at the university can directly or indirectly influence the professional development of students' mental functions. Clarification of the importance of the future profession, work responsibilities, and accumulation of knowledge cause the desired changes in the direction of cognitive processes.

Exercises aimed at those analyzers that play a leading role in fulfilling future work responsibilities have a great impact on the professional development of sensory-perceptual components. For the professional development of students' feelings and perceptions, it is necessary to acquaint them with the appearance, signs of objects, phenomena that are included in their work activities.

When forming attention, the specificity of professional requirements for both attention in general and its properties is taken into account. For example, the teacher's attention should be easily switched and distributed, characterized by sufficient stability, volume, and concentration.

Continuous practical training of students at our institute provides for the gradual acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities of the main functional areas of pedagogical activity. It is possible to identify specific difficulties during the passage of pedagogical practice. Most students take a long time to get used to working with primary school children. Students have doubts about their abilities, some dislike or indifference to their future profession, or doubts about the correctness of their choice.

Some individual psychological characteristics of students may negatively affect the process of adaptation to new conditions of internship. These are disadvantages of the cognitive sphere, deficiencies in the development of attention, low self-esteem, increased anxiety and lack of practical skills.

The formation of socio-psychological adaptability is important for a future teacher. This is a state of relationship between a person and a group, when a person, without prolonged external and internal conflicts, productively performs his leading activity, fully meets those role expectations. The formation of attention and its properties in students involves influencing the orientation of their personality, will, and attitude to work. Attention and attentiveness are formed in students in the process of active learning activities. Students' memory develops in the course of their activities. At the same time, its professionalization is observed.

The student – future teacher develops a memory for people, for children, he remembers better the manifestation of their feelings, behavioral characteristics, biographical information. It is necessary to purposefully develop and improve students' memory in accordance with the requirements of their future profession.

It is necessary not only to memorize well and keep in mind the necessary knowledge in the future, but also to be always ready for their rapid and accurate reproduction in the conditions of professional activity. Any profession places high demands on the thinking of a specialist.

It should be mobile, flexible and fast. In order to form professional thinking among students, it is necessary to equip them with a system of concepts and knowledge necessary to complete the tasks of future work. In the available research, pedagogical thinking is considered as the ability to identify and solve pedagogical problems, the characteristics of the qualities of the teacher's mind are given, the transition to the study of thinking and its meaningful side is carried out (N.V. Kuzmina).

The following research methods were used: analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature on the research problem; empirical methods; study and generalization of teaching experience; pedagogical experiment.

During the study of psychological and pedagogical literature, a theoretical analysis of the essence and content of the features of preparing students for professional pedagogical activity in the aspect of psychological and pedagogical problems was carried out. In the process of educational work at school, it was revealed that pedagogical practice and the use of psychological trainings contribute to the development of professional skills and personal qualities.

Based on the reports of pedagogical practice, it can be concluded that in the group engaged in the application of the developed psychological and pedagogical material, students showed higher results of professional preparedness.

It is revealed that pedagogical practice and materials developed on psychological and pedagogical support ensure the formation of professional readiness of future primary school teachers and increase the psychological readiness of students to become teachers.

Psychological and pedagogical support, which ensures the formation of professional readiness of future teachers, includes: assisting students in developing their own method of educational and cognitive interaction, including individual classes in the training and modeling stage of preparation, taking into account the personal psychological characteristics of individual students, creating an inextricable link between the practical participation of students in real professional activities. By creating these conditions in the process of professional training of students, we will get a sought-after and competitive specialist.

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